

Project Management, Leadership and Skills: Planning and Control

Author: [Eltigani Musa](#)

Abstract:

Leadership is recognized to be an important concept that has gained particularly significant attention in the 20th century, during which were developed main leadership theories. By the end of the 1990s, there were developed and popularized six major schools of leadership theory, including: the trait school, the behavioral school, the contingency school, the charismatic/visionary school, the emotional intelligence school, and the competency school (Turner & Müller, 2005). Each school has developed a set of criteria, characteristics, competencies, etc. of different types of leadership, which are widely applied in managerial practice until today. These leadership theories are applicable to different organizational context and activities, including project management. Among a variety of existing leadership theories, many researchers suggest that transactional and transformational leadership styles related to the charismatic leadership school are the most commonly practiced and effective styles in project management. The research of this paper also indicates that the right balance of both task-oriented and people-oriented leadership approach is especially relevant to the project management environment, whereas team work is especially important to project success. However, the research also indicates that there is no universal leadership style, which could fit practically any project management context. Different approach of leadership act differently (either worse or better) on different types of change projects and at different life cycle stages of these projects. Therefore, project manager needs to be able to adopt appropriate leadership style in order to achieve positive results, high level of productivity and enhanced team performance. Moreover, in today's diverse environments, project managers need to be able to adjust to various socio-cultural

contexts and adopt appropriate communication style in order to succeed in project implementation.

1. Introduction

In the 20th century leadership role is perceived to be a far-reaching concept that has exceptionally achieved a significant attention. Currently, there are published so many books, academic papers and empirical studies devoted to leadership and its role in contemporary business environment and society as a whole.

Project management also has been significantly influenced by changes of external environment, technological breakthroughs, globalization, IT development, etc. While in the 20th century project leadership was mainly focused on such basic performance indicators as time, cost, quality and return on investment, in the 21st century, project managers are challenged by intercultural communication, management of virtual teams, stakeholder management, knowledge sharing, ethical behavior, etc. (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011; Nauman et al., 2009).

In order to manage projects in the 21st century, project managers have to adopt different approaches, acquire new skills and apply appropriate leadership styles in order to fit the situation or context (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011). Lloyd-Walker and Walker (2011) suggest that modern project managers need to develop new leadership styles that will allow them to meet all the challenges and opportunities faced today.

This paper aims to analyze the role of leadership and communication in project management process and to discuss critically the role of leadership style and team building in project management utilizing appropriate theoretical models to identify how project staff can be led and motivated depending on project and its life-cycle.

2. Six major schools of leadership theory

The concept of leadership has been significantly changing during the history of humankind. This evolution resulted in development of many different definitions and interpretations of the term “leadership” (Yang). The most common definition of leadership is given as follows: “leadership is dynamic, which is the ability to influence

groups for purposes of goal accomplishment” (Koontz and Wehrich, 1990 cited in Yang et al., 2011:259). According to Bernard (1938), leadership was defined as an individual’s capability to perform two different types of functions: cognitive (managerial) and cathetic (emotional). Managerial functions or cognitive functions would include such functions as directing and guiding people’s actions and choices, while cathetic functions would cover motivational and emotional elements of goal-setting, inspiration, commitment, etc. (Turner & Müller, 2005). While the Bernard’s (1938) theories on leadership are still relevant and applicable in today’s business environment, over the last decades, the theory of leadership has evolved significantly. This continuous change and development of management achieve resulted in development of six major schools of leadership theory, including: the trait school, the behavioral school, the contingency school, the charismatic/visionary school, the emotional intelligence school, and the competency school (Turner & Müller, 2005). Each school has developed a set of criteria, characteristics, competencies, etc. of different types of leadership, which are widely applied in managerial practice until today.

- **The trait school of leadership**

The trait school of leadership gained its recognition in the 1930-1940s, when leaders’ traits such as personality, abilities and physical appearance served as the key determiners and characteristics of leader (Turner & Müller, 2010). Personality included such traits as emotional variables and self-confidence, abilities included hard management skills, while physical appearance included body size and appearance of leader (Turner & Müller, 2005).

- **The behavior school of leadership**

In the 1940s, there emerged the behavior school of leadership, which emphasized the flexibility and adaptation of leader’s behavior to particular leadership task (Turner & Müller, 2010). This school introduced a new insight that leadership was something that could be learned rather than a talent given with birth. The basic set of leadership parameters defined by the behavioral leadership school encompass: care for people or

relationships, care for production, use of authority, participation of team in managerial decision-making, and resilience vs following the rules (Turner & Müller, 2005).

- **The contingency school of leadership**

In the 1960s, greater popularity was gained by the contingency school of leadership, according to which the appropriateness of leadership style depended on different situations and leaders' personal characteristics. In order to define the most efficient leadership style it was necessary to evaluate the leader's characteristics, analyze the situation, and to match the leader to situation (Turner & Müller, 2005). Based on the contingency theory, increasing popularity gained the path-goal theory, according to which leader was responsible for helping a team to find the path to achieve the set goals and provide relevant assistance and support to them during this process (Turner & Müller, 2005). There were offered four different styles of path-goal theory of leadership: directive, supportive, participative and achievement oriented (Turner & Müller, 2005).

- **Charismatic or visionary school of leadership**

In the 1980s, the leadership theory was enriched by charismatic or visionary leadership. This leadership theory was associated with an organizational change and offered two different leadership styles: transactional and transformational style (Turner & Müller, 2010). Transactional leadership theory emphasized contingent reward system, whereas team members/followers were rewarded for achieving performance goals. Involvement of management/leadership was minimized to the situations when something went wrong/not as planned (Turner & Müller, 2005). Transformational leadership, on the contrary, required development of vision, exposure of charisma, and engendering of respect, pride and trust (Turner & Müller, 2005). Transformational leaders are expected to motivate and inspire their followers, considering personalities and displacing respect to the individuals. Continuous intellectual stimulation and encouraging for new ideas are the other important attributes of transformational leaders (Turner & Müller, 2005).

- **The emotional intelligence school of leadership**

In the late 1990s, there emerged the emotional intelligence school of leadership, which placed a significant focus on interaction management and self-management (Turner & Müller, 2010). This style of leadership has been broken down into six additional types of leadership including: visionary, coaching, affiliative, democratic, pacesetter and commanding (Turner & Müller, 2010). The first four of these leadership styles encourage and foster team work, while the last two styles are supposed to be applied in special circumstances for correcting the situation (Turner & Müller, 2005).

- **The competency school of leadership**

Finally, the most recent developments in leadership theory were developed by the competency school of leadership. This school is based on the theory of leader's competence— "a specific combination of knowledge, skills and personal characteristics" (cited in Turner & Müller, 2010:438). This theory implies that different combinations of leadership competencies will lead to different leadership styles that fit specific context/environment.

Such a chronological overview of the development of leadership theories might be useful in further analysis of how the concept of leadership was integrated and adjusted in project management.

3. Leadership in Project Management

There are many different approaches to leadership, which greatly vary in terms of the role of leader in a project and the way leader communicates and cooperates with the stakeholders. Among a variety of existing leadership theories, many researchers suggest that transactional and transformational leadership styles related to the charismatic leadership school are the most commonly practiced and effective styles in project management (Yang et al., 2011). As Whetten and Cameron (2016:515) explain, for project leaders "The key is to have a balance between task-oriented roles and relationship-building roles displayed in the team to avoid the downfall of many teams...who become one dimensional".

- **Transactional leadership**

Transactional leadership was widely accepted leadership style in the beginning of the 21 century, when compliance to the book rules and standard methodologies was highly valued by both project team members and project sponsors (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011). However, with the shift from manual physical work to knowledge-based projects, the relevance of transactional leadership style has been greatly diminished. Still, some researchers explain that due to the specifics of the project management science, which implies that a project is a set of well-planned tasks, project managers tend to demonstrate task-oriented rather than people-oriented leadership style (Turner & Müller, 2005). While transactional leadership style is less popular today, it still can be appropriate for “highly process-oriented projects” (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011: 386). Also, this approach may be especially appropriate to projects carried out in relevant socio-cultural contexts. Thus, for example, an empirical study has shown that in Asia effective leadership style in projects is characterized by low task but high relationship attitudes (Walker and Kalinowski, 1994).

- **Transformational leadership**

Another leadership theory, which has gained its widespread acceptance in project management, is **transformational leadership**. In today’s knowledge-driven economy, people cannot be treated anymore as robots or machines as they require more sophisticated approach to “people management” (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011: 386). Both these leadership styles are applied in PM, but its relevance depends on the complexity of a project. The empirical study carried out by Turner & Müller (2010) also supports this claim, as researcher conclude that concern for process under transactional leadership is more relevant and important on relatively simple projects. However, more-demanding and complicated projects require greater concern for people, foreseen under the transformational leadership (Turner & Müller, 2010).

Furthermore, in order to fill the existing gap in project management literature, Turner & Müller (2007) carried out an empirical study, interviewing 400 project managers. The

study has shown that the project manager’s leadership style is an important factor in the process of assigning “right” project manager to specific project, especially it relates to complex projects. Furthermore, the researchers concluded that among a variety of different leadership competencies, the ability to communicate, sensitivity and conscientiousness were highly correlated to project success (Turner, & Müller, 2007). All these competencies are more associated with transformational leadership style, which has been previously discussed.

4. Project management leadership in different project life-cycles

Project management always is associated with change management. Many experts believe that there is no universal leadership style, which could fit practically any project management context. As Dulewicz and Higgs (2003) explain, different styles of leadership perform differently (either worse or better {Table 1}) on different types of change projects and at different life cycle stages of these projects. Thus, for example, the researchers, identified 15 leadership dimensions that could be used to analyze and evaluate project manager’s performance.

Leadership style	Relatively stable	Context-significant change	Transformational change
Goal-oriented	Good fit	Moderate fit	Poor fit
Involving	Moderate fit	Good fit	Moderate fit
Engaging	Poor fit	Moderate fit	Good fit

Table 1: Performance of different leadership styles on different types of change projects (Source: Turner, & Müller, 2005).

Hauschild et al. (2000) also have emphasized the importance of matching different leadership styles to different types of projects, offering a categorization of project managers in terms of their leadership approaches. These categories include project star, focused creative expert, promising new comer, uncreative decision maker, and thick-

skinned pragmatist. Each type of project leader was supposed to be adopted in projects varying in terms of budget size, project prioritization, need for technology skills, access and provision of information, etc. (Turner, & Müller, 2010).

5. Leadership in project management and project success

In contrast to general management theories, project management literature shows lower reinforcement of the role of leadership style and leadership competencies to the success of the project. However, along with the evolution of project management science there is observed increased reinforcement of the role of leadership in project success. Thus, for example, Morris (1988) developed a list of both failure and success factors. According to Morris (1998), poor leadership should be referred to the failure factor at the stage of formation, build-up and close-out of the project, but not at the execution stage (Turner & Müller, 2005). However, the author greatly refers to the cognitive and cathectic roles defined by Barnard, which do imply some key leadership traits and behaviors. Another study, carried out by Morris and Hough (1987) also supported the theory of Barnard's cognitive and cathectic roles. The authors have carried out an empirical study of seven UK projects, both successful and failed and defined the factors predetermining success of the project. Later, the list of factors was transformed into the Seven Forces Model for project success by Turner (1999), which included a set of factors, broken down into six categories, including (1) context, (2) attitudes, (3) sponsorship, (4) definition, (5) people, and (6) systems. The success factors under category "people" also included leadership (Turner & Müller, 2005).

6. Project Manager's Leadership style and Teamwork

An overview of different categorizations and types of leadership demonstrate different approach to team management skills that leaders are expected to possess in order to succeed. Yang et al. (2011) have carried out an empirical industry-wide study in order to evaluate the association among project manager's leadership style, teamwork and project success. Based on the research findings, the authors concluded charismatic leadership and teamwork are positively interrelated in project management field. Yang et al. (2011)

explained that the project managers who apply transactional and transformational leadership styles have greater chances to improve team collaboration, team communication, and team cohesiveness. Improved team performance and greater team collaboration positively contribute to the project success in terms of both stakeholder satisfaction and quality, budget and schedule performance (Yang et al., 2011). An important role of leader's skills of inspiring, influencing and persuading is especially notable in IT projects, whereas team work, support, commitment and collaboration are crucial to the long-term success of the project and business as a whole (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011).

In order to better illustrate the role of leadership on team performance and overall success to the project, it is possible to refer to the case laid out by (Kliem and Anderson, 2003). As Kliem and Anderson (2003) explain, the main responsibility of a project manager is to develop a project plan, to identify project milestones and tasks and to assign people responsible for completing these tasks. While in theory everything seems to be simple, in practice, project manager often faces with a challenge of mismatching. It often happens that people assigned for a project lack talents, skills, desire, motivation or knowledge in order to successfully complete their tasks (Kliem and Anderson, 2003). This mismatch can confuse and frustrate not only a project manager but all project team members. Such a mismatch is more likely to cause a role conflict as well as intragroup conflict (Kliem and Anderson, 2003). Project manager who is not able to adopt appropriate leadership style will not be able to achieve positive results, high level of productivity and enhanced team performance (Kliem and Anderson, 2003). The role of two-ways communication also is crucial in project management as it allows project manager to develop trustful and collaborative relationships with team members and other stakeholders. Any potential conflict or disagreement can be managed and resolved without posing a threat of interpersonal and/or intragroup conflicts (Kliem and Anderson, 2003).

The critical importance of leadership is also reinforced with the development of such trend as virtual teams in project management. With increasing globalization, IT

development, liberalization of international trade and labour markets, many projects nowadays involve virtual teams, which often are comprised of diverse people with different cultural and social backgrounds. Nauman et al. (2009) have carried out an empirical study in order to evaluate the role of leadership style in project management and virtual team management. The researchers explained that virtual teams need more empowerment and greater concern for people. However, it is still important to recognize cross-cultural differences among team members as nations with culturally-ordered hierarchies do not usually want to accept responsibility and prefer to delegate it to project managers and leaders (Tuuli et al., 2012). Therefore, project managers need to be able to adjust to diverse socio-cultural contexts and adopt appropriate communication style in order to succeed in project implementation.

7. Conclusion

The concept of leadership has been significantly changing during the history of humankind. This continuous change and development of management achieve resulted in development of six major schools of leadership theory, including: the trait school, the behavioral school, the contingency school, the charismatic/visionary school, the emotional intelligence school, and the competency school (Turner & Müller, 2005). Each school has developed a set of criteria, characteristics, competencies, etc. of different types of leadership, which are widely applied in managerial practice until today. Practically every of the above mentioned leadership theories have been applied to greater or to smaller extent to project management field. In order to manage projects in the 21st century, project managers have to adopt different approaches, acquire new skills and apply appropriate leadership styles in order to fit the situation or context (Lloyd-Walker and Walker, 2011). However, among a broad range of leadership theories, significant amount of empirical studies provide evidence that transformational and transactional leadership theories are the most common and relevant to project management. Project managers are responsible for acting as leaders in developing a teamwork and collaboration in the project group/team, which are crucial to the project success. As the research indicates, different leadership styles are appropriate at different stages of the

product life cycle. Modern project managers need to develop new leadership styles that will allow them to meet all the challenges and opportunities faced today. The leadership style for specific project, team, and phase of the project should be determined by evaluation of both internal and external variables. Moreover, with the increased popularity of diverse and virtual teams, project managers also have to be able to adjust to diverse socio-cultural contexts and adopt appropriate communication style in order to succeed in project implementation.

References:

Barnard, C.I. (1938). *The functions of the executive*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.

Dulewicz, V. and Higgs, M.J. (2003). *Design of a new instrument to assess leadership dimensions and styles*. Henley Working Paper Series. Henley-on-Thames, UK: Henley Management College.

Frame, J.D. (1987). *Managing projects in organizations*. San Francisco: Jossey Bass.

Hauschildt, J., Keim, G. and Medcof, J. (2000). Realistic criteria for project manager selection and development. *Project Management Journal* 31(3), pp.23-32.

Lloyd-Walker, B. and Walker, D. (2011). Authentic leadership for 21st century project delivery. *International Journal of Project Management*, 29, pp.383-395.

Matthews, R., & McLees, J. (2015). Building effective projects teams and teamwork. *Journal of Information Technology and Economic Development*, 6(2), 20-30.

Morris, P.W.G. (1997). *The management of projects*. 2nd ed. London: Thomas Telford.

Morris, P.W.G. (1987). *The anatomy of major projects: a study of the reality of project management*. Chichester, UK: Wiley.

Nauman, S., Khan, A. and Ehsan, N. (2009). Patterns of empowerment and leadership style in project management. *International Journal of Project Management* 28, pp.638-649.

Robbins, S.P. (1997). *Essential of organizational behavior*. Prentice Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.

Turner, J.R. (1999). *The handbook of project-based management: improving the process for achieving strategic objectives*. London: McGraw-Hill.

Turner, J, & Müller, R (2005), The project manager's leadership style as a success factor on projects: a literature review. *Project Management Journal*, 36, 2, pp. 49-61, Business Source Complete, EBSCOhost, viewed 12 August 2016.

Turner, R. & Müller, J. (2007). Matching the project manager's leadership style to project type. *International Journal of Project Management* 25, pp. 21-32.

Turner, R., & Müller, R. (2010). Leadership competency profiles of successful project managers. *International Journal of Project Management*, 28, pp. 437-448.

Tuuli, M., Rowlinson, S. Fellows, R. and Liu, A. (2012). Empowering the project team: impact of leadership style and team context. *Team performance Management: An international Journal*, 18 (3/4), pp.149-175.

Walker, A. and Kalinowski, M. (1994), An anatomy of a Hong Kong project – organization, environment and leadership. *Construction management and Economics*, 12, pp. 191-202.

Whetten, D.A. and Cameron, K.S. (2016). *Developing Management Skills*, 9th ed. New York, Prentice-Hall Project.

Yang, L., Huang, C. and Wu, K. (2011). The association among project manager's leadership style, teamwork and project success. *International Journal of Project Management*, 29, pp. 258-267.

Share this: